

Preferences of Dominican senior high students in selecting films

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Abstract

The purpose of this research is to identify the preference of the Dominican senior high school students in selecting films and to find out the possible factors affecting their preferences in favoring films. The research method used for this study is the descriptive research design. The respondents for this research are the grades 11 and 12 of the senior high department of the St Dominic College of Asia. Out of the 60 respondents, student responded that they "Moderately Preferred" to the theme as one of the preferences in selecting films with the average weighted mean of 3.37; they are "Moderately Preferred" to direction as one of the preferences in selecting films with the average weighted mean of 3.60; they are "Moderately Preferred" to casting as one of the preferences in selecting films with the average weighted mean of 3.92; they are "Extremely Preferred" to the genre as one of the preferences in selecting films with the average weighted mean of 4.18, and they are "Extremely Preferred" to the trailer as one of the preferences in selecting films with the average weighted mean of 4.01. The researchers recommended that movie directors could focus more on making films that were based on the preferred themes, genres, and casting of the youth today. Student filmmakers should consider relevant and timely themes and genres in making future films considering the youths of today as their audience. Movie producers can improve on audience impact of their film by showing the genre of the movie in trailers so that young viewers will easily screen the film based on their preference.

Keywords: Preference, films, senior high students, genre, theme, casting, trailer, direction.

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Introduction

Through the years, films have become an integral part of the people's lives for multiple reasons. Films have been with us and have positively affected us from gaining new knowledge or touching our heart in a very delicate way. It can either be a source of entertainment, a source of information, or a tool for education for things that are trending and needs attention. It can tackle the depressing events happening in our society, a strong tool for education. It can make us believe in love and leave us heartbroken with the tragic themes it may show to us. The researchers wanted to know if this is all that we could further stretch what the purpose of films to us human beings in our lives, in our values, and in our development in different aspects.

With so many films to pick from and available both in the cinema and online platforms, it became easier for most people, especially the young viewers, to have access to films. The researchers would like to dig deeper and understand how the preferences of young people change.

Each young individual has their own taste when it comes to films. It depends on the purpose when they buy a movie ticket or put out a smartphone to watch or stream movie on online streaming sites. An average person might want to watch a film just for leisure, or as a pastime. Another individual might watch a film for the purpose of analysis since they were given a task by their professor.

Depending on the age of the viewer, a preferred movie may differ. One movie might be too serious for a specific individual while another may contradict and find great interest on that film. Another individual might simply watch film just to ease their boredom and would rather watch light flicks or romantic comedy since their sole purpose is to be entertained.

To further strengthen the foundations of a young film viewer, one might consider knowing the past and know more about the films that were made long ago and how does the content of the movies changed throughout time. Reich (2017) states that the heart of the movie which is the theme is of great essence when you talk about films. It controls the flow of the film. It is the main reason moviegoers become who they are. There are other elements like characters, story, plot, cinematography, or genre but nothing beats the theme in importance. These elements show how the theme is manifested, yet most moviegoers are not aware, nor do they know what the role of theme is when they see a film. It even goes with them after watching the movie when they discuss it afterwards.

The person responsible for picking the theme is the producer. This person is also responsible for hiring and removal of the staff as well as looking for the budget for the film. After picking the theme for the movie, the producer then will hire a writer, for theme creation, and a director, to exhibit the theme through film. In other instances, the producer might look for a polished script suited for his or her preference for the theme. Once the construction of theme is finished, the script by this time should have a story or action, and a plot. Putting these two elements together builds the character development, which mirrors the theme. The meaning of the theme is provided by the elements of the story, plot, and character development.

After knowing what happened in the past and the way film was made, would a young viewer have a deeper sense of appreciation of these films? Would it matter to them? Is content authentic when it comes to creating media, or are there other considerations that affect viewers in their preferences?

Krämer (2005) said that to attract a huge audience, you have to hire popular actors and actresses. To receive awards, you have to make a film in a certain genre that will appeal to the award-giving bodies. Parallel to the movie goers' perspective, other viewers may watch a film that has popular actors and actresses since these personalities are already familiar to them. On the filmmaker's perspective, it may mean that it is easier to sell a well-known product, i.e., the popular actors, to the young market.

The premises above prompt the researchers to conduct the study about the preferences of Dominican senior high school students in selecting films. The study aims to help them understand the preferences behind the selection of films. Specifically, it sought to determine the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, gender, and family income; to determine the level of preferences of the respondents in selecting films in terms of theme, casting, direction, genre, and trailer; and to identify if there a significant relationship between the level of preferences and the demographic profile of the respondents in selecting mainstream films.

Related Literature

The preference of the viewers in terms of theme are discussed by Zwier (2012) which states that the implicit and explicit messages present in teenage films' portrayal of teenage romantic relationships so as to better understand the possible influences of the messages present in these films as teens seek them out for information and advice about romantic relationships; Banerjee et al. (2008) which proves that happy films and high arousal films were favored rather than sad and low arousal films; and Tanpipat et al. (2016) which reveals that for movie selections the people of Bangkok are more into content and type of film.

When it comes to casting in films, Sanchez et al. (2016) stated that movies such as of Kris Aquino are vis-à-vis a remarkable horror genre in regards to her title as the "Philippine Box Office Horror Queen; and Tugano (2021) also proves that the effectiveness of the actors and the settings of the film which depicts the reality, representation, and the sense of love in the representation of Filipinos in other countries.

In terms of direction, some movies were discussed by Capino (2018) which states that the films of Lino Brocka is what made him one of the critically acclaimed directors to be known in the Philippines; Bradshaw (2016) which reveals that director Brillante Mendoza loves to make films that depict the sad reality of the environment that gave him a lot of film awards and recognition; and Aguilar (2019) which reveals that in an interview of one of the famous director in the Philippines, Cathy Garcia-Molina, she stated that actor John Lloyd Cruz wants to do another movie with her. Given the awards and abilities of Garcia-Molina to direct movies, one of the reasons Cruz wants to do another movie with the award-winning director.

The preferences according to gender in movies are simply discussed by Fradera (2016) which states that one possible reason for the gender difference is that females pay greater attention to romantic comedies, while males pay closer attention to action. While Shary (2014) proves that preferred movies by Americans are mostly set in high school and also found out that female teenagers are more into drama and romance. On the other hand, male teenagers are more into violence and action type of movies.

The viewers' family income is discussed by Gennetian et al. (2010) which states that income represented as the purest monetary transfer for increasing the purchasing power of low-income families. Social scientists have made great methodological strides in establishing whether income has independent effects on the cognitive development of low-income children. Rustin (2017) proves that a low household income can affect the child's cognitive and physical health.

Methodology

This research utilized the descriptive research design as the researchers' goal is to describe the data gathered from the selected respondents. This research method is best applied as the purpose of this study is to rate or describe the preferences of the respondents in selecting mainstream films.

The senior high school students at St. Dominic College of Asia were used as the respondents in this study. These samples were chosen using cluster sampling technique by dividing

the whole population into two separate clusters: grades 11 and 12. The researchers then selected one (1) section from grade 11 and one (1) section from grade 12 as their respondents.

The questionnaire is divided into two (2) parts: (1) the demographic profile of the respondents; and (2) the preferences of the respondents in selecting mainstream films. The questionnaire was sent to the adviser and statistician for validation before they were used in data gathering.

After the approval and validation of the questionnaires, which were used in gathering the data, a request letter was sent to the School Principal of Senior High School at St. Dominic College of Asia to request permission of recruiting selected students from the male and female population to be part of the respondents. The gathering of data was done thereafter by distributing each survey questionnaire through google online survey form. The results were then analyzed and interpreted to arrive valid conclusions. Each item in the questionnaires was measured using appropriate statistical tools. To interpret the rating of their responses, the corresponding quantitative descriptions were considered. The results were used as basis in determining the preferences of the respondents in selecting films.

This study used percentage and frequency distribution to measure the demographic profile of the respondents, while the weighted mean was used as a statistical tool to determine the preferences of the respondents in selecting mainstream films.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. Demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
15-16	10	16.7%
17-18	48	80.0%
19 and above	2	3.3%
Total	60	100%

Table 1 shows that majority or 80% of the respondents belong to 17 to 18 years old and ten (10) or 16.7% belong 15 to 16 years of age. Only two (2) out of 60 respondents belong to 19 years old and above.

Table 2. Demographic profile of the respondents in terms of gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	11	18.3%
Female	49	81.7%
Total	60	100%

Table 2 shows that forty-nine (49) or 81.7% of the respondents are female and eleven (11) or 18.3% are male. The result reveals that women are more onto movies, rather than men. Women are easy to catch when it comes to movies, unlike men all they care about is action or sometimes they do not really watch movies.

Table 3. Demographic profile of the respondents in terms of family income

Family Income	Frequency	Percentage
Below 11,000	3	5.0%
11,000-20,000	10	16.7%
20,001-30,000	1	1.7%
30,001-40,000	11	18.3%
40,001-50,000	14	23.3%
50,001 and above	21	35.0%
Total	60	100%

Based on Table 3, twenty-one (21) or 35% of the respondents have monthly family income of Php 51,000 and above, fourteen (14) or 23.3% have Php 41,000 to Php 50,000, eleven (11) or 18.3% have Php 31,000 to Php 40,000, ten (10) or 16.7% have Php 11,000 to Php 20,000, and three (3) or 5% have below Php 11,000. Only one (1) or 1.7% falls under family income of Php 21,000 to Php 30,000. Family income is essential because a person cannot watch a movie if he or she does not have money, because normally we prioritize what the family needs; food, shelter and utilities and among others.

Table 4. Factors affecting the preferences of the respondents in terms of theme

Statement	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. I watch the film with a theme that I can relate with my personal life.	3.00	Preferred
2. I watch the film with a theme that affects my emotional state.	3.53	Moderately preferred
3. I watch the film with theme that is timely in present day society.	3.58	Moderately preferred
AVERAGE	3.37	Moderately preferred

Legend: 5 – Extremely preferred; 4 – Moderately preferred; 3 – Preferred; 2 – Slightly preferred; 1 – Not preferred

The average weighted mean is 3.37 which means that the respondents are "Moderately Preferred" to theme as one of the preferences in selecting mainstream films. The results correlate that one should be satisfied in watching a movie, if the theme were not emphasized clearly it would be a waste of time and money.

Table 5. Factors affecting the preferences of the respondents in terms of direction

Statement	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. I watch films because of the edit treatment.	2.72	Preferred
2. I watch the film because the direction is good.	3.88	Moderately preferred
3. I watch the film because the director showed the plot well.	4.20	Extremely preferred
AVERAGE	3.60	Moderately preferred

Legend: 5 – Extremely preferred; 4 – Moderately preferred; 3 – Preferred; 2 – Slightly preferred; 1 – Not preferred

The average weighted mean is 3.60 which means that the respondents are "Moderately Preferred" to direction as one of the preferences in selecting mainstream films. The results are going to be useless if the good theme of the film was not properly directed. When one's hobby is watching movies, it is easy for him or her to know the capability of the directors or what this director can do or how this director can run the whole movie or what we call "trademark", and for that when he or she is with someone and they are not sure of which movie they are going to watch, he or she can easily prefer or recommend that type of movie based on the director.

Table 6. Factors affecting the preferences of the respondents in terms of casting

Statement	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. I watch the film because the actors fit the role well.	4.07	Extremely preferred
2. I watch the film because of the actor's/actress' portrayal.	4.20	Extremely preferred
3. I watch the film because of my interest in the cast.	3.50	Moderately preferred
AVERAGE	3.92	Moderately preferred

Legend: 5 – Extremely preferred; 4 – Moderately preferred; 3 – Preferred; 2 – Slightly preferred; 1 – Not preferred

The average weighted mean is 3.92 which means that the respondents are "Moderately Preferred" to casting as one of the preferences in selecting mainstream films. Casting is particularly important, especially this gives encouragement to view the film because they know that having popular cast would be a good movie.

Table 7. Factors affecting the preferences of the respondents in terms of genre

Statement	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. I watched the film based on the genre.	3.87	Moderately preferred
2. I watch the film because it catches my attention.	4.42	Extremely preferred
3. I watch the film because of the concept.	4.26	Extremely preferred
AVERAGE	4.18	Extremely preferred

Legend: 5 – Extremely preferred; 4 – Moderately preferred; 3 – Preferred; 2 – Slightly preferred; 1 – Not preferred

The average weighted mean is 4.18 which means that the respondents are "Extremely Preferred" to genre as one of the preferences in selecting mainstream films. This is what tickles the mind of the moviegoers, if one is highly addicted to horror films, regardless of who the cast is as long as it satisfies his/her preferred genre. But sometimes it depends on the person's emotions of what type of movie s/he views.

Table 8. Factors affecting the preferences of the respondents in terms of trailer

Statement	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. The trailer of the film makes me excited.	4.13	Extremely preferred
2. The trailer of the film meets my expectation about the movie.	3.73	Moderately preferred
3. The trailer of the film catches my attention to watch the movie.	4.18	Extremely preferred
AVERAGE	4.01	Extremely preferred

Legend: 5 – Extremely preferred; 4 – Moderately preferred; 3 – Preferred; 2 – Slightly preferred; 1 – Not preferred

The average weighted mean is 4.01 which means that the respondents are "Extremely Preferred" to trailer as one of the preferences in selecting mainstream films. The trailer serves as an "appetizer." This gives the moviegoer an idea about the outcome of the movie. There may be some loopholes but once a person watches the movie, all questions will be answered.

Table 9. Correlations between the average preferences and age

		Average Preferences	Age
Average Preferences	Pearson Correlation	1	-0.115
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.383
	N	60	60
Age	Pearson Correlation	-0.115	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.383	
	N	60	60

Legend: ± 1.00 = Perfect Positive/Negative Correlation; ± 0.51 to 0.99 = High or Strong Positive/Negative Correlation; ± 0.50 = Some Positive/Negative Correlation; ± 0.49 to 0.01 = Small or Weak Positive/Negative Correlation; 0.00 = No Correlation

Table 9 above shows the result of the relationship between the average preferences and age of the respondents. IBM SPSS was utilized to obtain the results on Pearson Correlation among the sixty (60) responses. The result with critical values $P > 0.05$ implies to accept null hypothesis (H_0). The absolute computed value of -0.115 is less than the critical value 0.383 measured at 0.05 level of significance. The computed Pearson Correlation value $r = -0.115$ indicates small negative correlation. Hence, results revealed that there is a weak relationship between the preferences and age of the respondents.

Table 10. Correlations between the average preferences and gender

		Average Preferences	Gender
Average Preferences	Pearson Correlation	1	-0.144
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.273
	N	60	60
Gender	Pearson Correlation	-0.144	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.273	
	N	60	60

Legend: ± 1.00 = Perfect Positive/Negative Correlation; ± 0.51 to 0.99 = High or Strong Positive/Negative Correlation; ± 0.50 = Some Positive/Negative Correlation; ± 0.49 to 0.01 = Small or Weak Positive/Negative Correlation; 0.00 = No Correlation

Table 10 above shows the result of the relationship between the average preferences and age of the respondents. The result with critical values $P > 0.05$ implies to accept null hypothesis (H_0). The absolute computed value of -0.114 is less than the critical value 0.273 measured at 0.05 level of significance. The computed Pearson Correlation value $r = -0.114$ indicates small negative correlation. Hence, results revealed that there is weak relationship between the preferences and gender of the respondents.

Table 11. Correlations between the average preferences and income

		Average Preferences	Income
Average Preferences	Pearson Correlation	1	-0.086
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.512
	N	60	60
Income	Pearson Correlation	-0.086	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.512	
	N	60	60

Legend: ± 1.00 = Perfect Positive/Negative Correlation; ± 0.51 to 0.99 = High or Strong Positive/Negative Correlation; ± 0.50 = Some Positive/Negative Correlation; ± 0.49 to 0.01 = Small or Weak Positive/Negative Correlation; 0.00 = No Correlation

Table 11 above shows the result of the relationship between the average preferences and age of the respondents. The result with critical values $P > 0.05$ implies to accept null hypothesis (H_0). The absolute computed value of -0.086 is less than the critical value 0.512 measured at 0.05 level of significance. The computed Pearson Correlation value $r = -0.086$ indicates small negative correlation. Hence, results revealed that there is a weak relationship between the preferences and gender of the respondents.

Based on the results, it shows that the demographic profile, such as age, gender and family income, do not affect their preference in selecting a film. Furthermore, the study shows a weak relationship between identifying demographic status and film preference of the respondents.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The following conclusions are drawn based on the summary of findings presented above. The researchers conclude that most of the viewers of films are middle teenagers who belong to the middle-class family. It is also observed that most of them are female which outnumber the male respondents. When it comes to the respondents' preferences and basing on the scale values and verbal interpretation that were used in determining the preferences of the respondents, the researchers conclude that the viewers are extremely preferred to genre and trailer, and moderately preferred in casting, direction, and theme in selecting films. This means that the five factors presented in the study have great effect on the preferences of the viewers in viewing movies. The age, gender, and family income of the viewers do not affect with their preferences in selecting films.

Movie directors could focus more on making films that are based on the preferred themes, genres and casting of the youth today. Directors should create more films that show social relevance especially to youths and women. Student film makers should consider making films that are both relatable to the preferences of both genders specially men. Movie producers and directors can level up their audience impact in regard to their film by making catchy teasers or trailers. The future researchers who want to expand this study could consider some other factors such as the availability of the cinema houses on watching films on malls, the working adults, and other reasons on how this factor affects their preference in selecting films to watch.

References

- Aguilar, K. (2019, August 8). *John Lloyd wants Cathy Molina-directed comeback movie*. Philippine Daily Inquirer. <https://entertainment.inquirer.net/341347/john-lloyd-wants-cathy-molina-directed-comeback-movie>
- Banerjee, S. C., Greene, K., Krcmar, M., Bagdasarov, Z., & Ruginyte, D. (2008). The role of gender and sensation seeking in film choice: Exploring mood and arousal. *Journal of Media Psychology: Theories, Methods, and Applications*, 20(3), 97–105. <https://doi.org/10.1027/1864-1105.20.3.97>

- Bradshaw, P. (2016, May 18). *Ma'Rosa review: A cold, hard look at what it means to be poor*. The Guardian. <https://www.theguardian.com/film/2016/may/18/marosa-review-brillante-mendoza-cannes>
- Capino, J. B. (2018, June 12). *Manila in the Claws of Light: A Proletarian inferno*. The Criterion Collection. <https://www.criterion.com/current/posts/5741-manila-in-the-claws-of-light-a-proletarian-inferno>
- Fradera, A. (2016, August 8). *Gender differences at the movies – women remember more of rom-coms, men remember more from action flicks*. BPS Research Digest. <http://bps-research-digest.blogspot.com/2016/08/gender-differences-at-movies-women.html>
- Gennetian, L., Castells, N., & Morris, P. A. (2010). Meeting the basic needs of children: Does income matter? *Children and Youth Services Review*, 32(9), 1138-1148. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.childyouth.2010.03.004>
- Krämer, P. (2005). *The new Hollywood: From Bonnie and Clyde to Star Wars*. Wallflower Press.
- Reich, J. (2017). *Exploring movie construction and production: What's so exciting about movies?* Open SUNY Textbooks. <https://knightscholar.geneseo.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1001&context=oer-ost>
- Rustin, S. (2017, July 12). *Household income plays crucial role in determining a child's prospects – report*. The Guardian. <https://www.theguardian.com/inequality/2017/jul/12/household-income-crucial-role-children-life-prospects-lse-report>
- Shary, T. (2014). *Generation multiplex: The image of youth in American cinema since 1980* (Revised ed.). University of Texas Press.
- Tanpipat, A., Kuawiriyapan, S., & Eiamcharoon, T. (2016). Factors affecting movie selection of audiences in Bangkok. In E. Shonin & M. Norihito (Eds.), *International conference proceedings of ICEHM and EAP* (pp. 23-26). <https://icehm.org/upload/4131ED1116026.pdf>
- Tugano, A. C. (2021). Representasyon ng kababaihang manggagawang Pilipino sa Europa batay sa pelikulang pag-ibig na Milan (2004) at Barcelona (2016) ni Olivia Lamasan. *Bisig Journal*, 3(1), 43-72. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/362668564_Representasyon_ng_Kababaihang_Manggagawang_Pilipino_sa_Europa_Batay_sa_Pelikulang_Pag-ibig_na_Milan_2004_at_Barcelona_2016_ni_Olivia_Lamasan
- Zwier, A. J. (2012). *Just another teen movie: analyzing portrayals of teenage romantic relationships across a decade of top-grossing teen films* (Doctoral dissertation, Colorado State University). https://mountainscholar.org/bitstream/handle/10217/67909/Zwier_colostate_0053N_11150.pdf